

Table 1 - Data on authorship, database affiliation, country, publication journal, and main topic, presented in chronological order.

Reference	Author (year)	Database	Country of study	Journal	Leptospirosis X Climate Change X Humans/Animals
[67]	Santos & Toledo Filho (2014)	Scopus	Brazil	Revista Brasileira de Meteorologia	Meteorological variable influences on hospital admissions
[216]	Agampodi <i>et al.</i> (2014)	Scopus	Sri Lanka	PLoS Neglected Tropical Diseases	Disease outbreak in humans in a dry region
[222]	Oliveira Filho <i>et al.</i> (2014)	Scopus	Brazil	Geospatial Health	Prevalence of leptospirosis in equids
[161]	Ridoutt <i>et al.</i> (2014)	Scopus	Australia	Australian Veterinary Journal	Detection of leptospirosis in feral pigs
[68]	Pagès <i>et al.</i> (2014)	Scopus	Reunion Island	International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health	Human leptospirosis
[121]	Pereira <i>et al.</i> (2014)	Scopus	Brazil	International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health	Social cost of leptospirosis cases
[46]	Guimarães <i>et al.</i> (2014)	Scopus	Brazil	Ciência & Saúde Coletiva	Positive effect of precipitation on transmission
[36]	Finger <i>et al.</i> (2014)	Scopus	Brazil	Revista do Instituto de Medicina Tropical de São Paulo	<i>Leptospira</i> spp. among cart horses from an endemic area of human leptospirosis
[122]	Usuzawa <i>et al.</i> (2014)	Scopus	Philippines	Tohoku Journal of Experimental Medicine	Awareness of disaster reduction frameworks and risk perception of natural disaster
[96]	Wang <i>et al.</i> (2014)	Pubmed	China	Biomedical and Environmental Sciences	An outbreak of leptospirosis linked to rainfall
[66]	Aragón-Martínez <i>et al.</i> (2014)	Scopus	Mexico	Journal of Wildlife Diseases	<i>Leptospira interrogans</i> in antillean manatees
[174]	Gracie <i>et al.</i> (2014)	Scopus	Brazil	International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health	Environmental and socioeconomic factors (densely urbanized areas, flood-prone regions, and altitude) in disease transmission

[173]	Wójcik-Fatla <i>et al.</i> (2014)	Pubmed	Poland	Annals of Agricultural and Environmental Medicine	Occurrence of pathogenic <i>Leptospira</i> in water and soil samples
[151]	Calvo-Cano <i>et al.</i> (2014)	Pubmed	Spain	Euro Surveillance	Cases of leptospirosis in travellers
[125]	Pimenta <i>et al.</i> (2014)	Scielo	Brazil	Pesquisa Veterinária Brasileira	Serovar prevalence in cattle
[103]	Weinberger <i>et al.</i> (2014)	Scopus	New Caledonia	PLoS Neglected Tropical Diseases	Leptospirosis outbreaks and climatic factors
[69]	Major <i>et al.</i> (2014)	Pubmed	Switzerland	International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health	Incidence of canine leptospirosis
[196]	Saito <i>et al.</i> (2014)	Pubmed	Philippines	Applied and Environmental Microbiology	Post-sea surge survival of <i>Leptospira</i>
[120]	McIver <i>et al.</i> (2015)	Scopus	Micronesia	Tropical Medicine and Health	Climate-sensitive infectious diseases
[37]	Lau <i>et al.</i> (2015)	Scopus	Australia	BMC Infectious Diseases	The emergence of <i>Leptospira borgpetersenii</i> serovar Arborea
[182]	Sánchez-Montes <i>et al.</i> (2015)	Scopus	Mexico	PLoS ONE	Human leptospirosis in Mexico
[97]	Vilain <i>et al.</i> (2015)	Scopus	Reunion Island	Prehospital and Disaster Medicine	Leptospirosis post-cyclone
[106]	Miklaušić <i>et al.</i> (2015)	Scopus	Croatia	Infektoloski Glasnik	Influence of rainfall, humidity, and air temperature on human leptospirosis
[126]	Suwanpakdee <i>et al.</i> (2015)	Pubmed	Thailand	Epidemiology and Infection	Influence of flooding on human disease
[199]	Matono <i>et al.</i> (2015)	Pubmed	Japan	Journal of Travel Medicine	Imported flood-related leptospirosis
[127]	Sohail <i>et al.</i> (2016)	Scopus	Pakistan	Journal of Equine Veterinary Science	Seroprevalence and risk factors in equines
[144]	Gonçalves <i>et al.</i> (2016)	Scielo	Brazil	Ciência & Saúde Coletiva	Leptospirosis space-time distribution and risk factors
[47]	Grayzel & DeBess (2016)	Scopus	USA	Journal of the American Medical Association	Geographical and temporal distributions of leptospirosis in dogs
[45]	Zhao <i>et al.</i> (2016)	Scopus	China	BMC Infectious Diseases	Environmental and socioeconomic factors associated with leptospirosis in China

[202]	Vinod Kumar <i>et al.</i> (2016)	Scopus	India	Letters in Applied Microbiology	<i>Leptospira</i> in environmental aquatic biofilms
[215]	Gloriani <i>et al.</i> (2016)	Scopus	Philippines	Southeast Asian Journal of Tropical Medicine and Public Health	Human seroprevalence of the disease after floods
[146]	Roxas <i>et al.</i> (2016)	Scopus	Philippines	Acta Medica Philippina	Leptospirosis outbreak after a heavy rainfall typhoon
[225]	Vieira <i>et al.</i> (2016)	Scopus	Brazil	Acta Tropica	Wild animals as carriers of <i>Leptospira</i> in the Pantanal biome
[38]	Christova & Tasseva (2016)	Scopus	Bulgaria	Problems of Infectious and Parasitic Diseases	Human leptospirosis
[39]	Londe <i>et al.</i> (2016)	Scopus	Brazil	Natural Hazards	Flood-related leptospirosis outbreaks
[29]	Lau <i>et al.</i> (2016)	Pubmed	Fiji	PLoS Neglected Tropical Diseases	Serovars involved and environmental factors
[162]	Widayani <i>et al.</i> (2016)	Scopus	Indonesia	Indonesian Journal of Geography	Vulnerable area model of Leptospirosis disease
[145]	Suriany <i>et al.</i> (2016)	Scopus	Indonesia	Journal of Pure and Applied Microbiology	Risk factors of human leptospirosis
[207]	Della Rossa <i>et al.</i> (2016)	Pubmed	Thailand	Epidemiology and Infection	Environmental factors and public health by leptospirosis
[189]	Benacer <i>et al.</i> (2016)	Pubmed	Malaysia	Acta Tropica	Epidemiology of leptospirosis and climatic factors
[105]	Habus <i>et al.</i> (2017)	Scopus	Croatia	Acta Tropica	Epidemiology of leptospirosis in Croatia
[183]	White <i>et al.</i> (2017)	Scopus	USA	The Veterinary Journal	Climatic correlations with canine leptospirosis
[152]	Silva <i>et al.</i> (2017)	Scopus	Brazil	Engenharia Sanitária e Ambiental	Sanitation and public health in hydrographic basin
[135]	Ledien <i>et al.</i> (2017)	Scopus	Cambodia	PloS ONE	Development of a flood indicator test
[49]	Jorge <i>et al.</i> (2017)	Scopus	Brazil	Travel Medicine and Infectious Disease	Association of human and animal leptospirosis with precipitation events
[109]	Joshi <i>et al.</i> (2017)	Scopus	Korea	BMC Infectious Diseases	Estimate the effect of climatic factors

[219]	Correia <i>et al.</i> (2017)	Scopus	Brazil	The Veterinary Journal	Effects of precipitation on infections in cattle
[70]	Santos <i>et al.</i> (2017)	Scopus	Brazil	Revista da Sociedade Brasileira de Medicina Tropical	Eco-epidemiological characterization of human leptospirosis
[48]	Sumi <i>et al.</i> (2017)	Scopus	Philippines	Epidemiology and Infection	Epidemiology of leptospirosis and climatic factors
[147]	Chaiblich <i>et al.</i> (2017)	Scielo	Brazil	Saúde em Debate	Human leptospirosis and risk factors
[155]	Chadsuthi <i>et al.</i> (2018)	Scopus	Thailand	BMC Infectious Diseases	Environmental factors in leptospirosis transmission in cattle and buffaloes
[164]	Ijaz <i>et al.</i> (2018)	Scopus	Pakistan	Pakistan Veterinary Journal	Sero-epidemiology of bovine leptospirosis and risk factors
[72]	Le Turnier <i>et al.</i> (2018)	Scopus	French Guiana	American Journal of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene	Epidemiology of human leptospirosis
[50]	Gutiérrez & Martínez-Veiga (2018)	Scopus	Colombia	Transactions of the Royal Society of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene	Spatiotemporal variability in the occurrence of human leptospirosis cases
[137]	Sohail <i>et al.</i> (2018)	Scopus	Pakistan	Acta Tropica	Human leptospirosis and risk factors
[163]	Syamsuar <i>et al.</i> (2018)	Scopus	Indonesia	Indian Journal of Public Health Research and Development	Leptospirosis in flood-prone areas
[226]	Rodríguez-Valero <i>et al.</i> (2018)	Scopus	Spain	Travel Medicine and Infectious Disease	Leptospirosis in Spanish travelers
[52]	Ghizzo Filho <i>et al.</i> (2018)	Scopus	Brazil	Revista do Instituto de Medicina Tropical de São Paulo	Temporal trend of human leptospirosis incidence
[154]	Ijaz <i>et al.</i> (2018)	Scopus	Pakistan	Acta Tropica	Seroprevalence and risk factors in cattle
[74]	Casanovas-Massana <i>et al.</i> (2018)	Pubmed	Brazil	Water research	<i>Leptospira</i> in surface waters from the urban slum environment
[73]	Cortez <i>et al.</i> (2018)	Scopus	Pakistan	Pakistan Veterinary Journal	Sero-epidemiology of bovine leptospirosis and associated risk factors

[30]	Vitale <i>et al.</i> (2018)	Pubmed	Italy	Journal of Infection and Public Health	Report of two symptomatic human leptospirosis cases
[31]	Matsushita <i>et al.</i> (2018)	Pubmed	Philippines	PLoS Neglected Tropical Diseases	Association of rainfall and disease occurrence in humans
[128]	Radi <i>et al.</i> (2018)	Pubmed	Malaysia	The American Journal of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene	Environmental factors such as floods and water bodies in disease distribution in humans
[51]	Mayfield <i>et al.</i> (2018)	Pubmed	Fiji	The Lancet Planetary Health	Use of geographically weighted logistic regression for human epidemiology
[218]	Silva <i>et al.</i> (2018)	Scielo	Brazil	Ciência & Saúde Coletiva	Risk factors for the occurrence of leptospirosis in dogs
[129]	Togami <i>et al.</i> (2018)	Pubmed	Fiji	The American Journal of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene	Occurrence of the disease in humans and factors such as floods
[187]	Baquero & Machado (2018)	Pubmed	Brazil	Scientific Reports	Spatiotemporal dynamics and risk factors for human leptospirosis
[75]	Dhewantara <i>et al.</i> (2018)	Pubmed	China	Scientific Reports	Geographical and temporal distribution of human leptospirosis
[100]	Dhewantara <i>et al.</i> (2019)	Scopus	China	Environmental Research	Temporal effects of climate on leptospirosis
[192]	Smith <i>et al.</i> (2019)	Scopus	USA	BMC Veterinary Research	Temporal trends and factors in canine leptospirosis
[165]	Blagojević <i>et al.</i> (2019)	Scopus	Serbia	Acta Veterinaria Hungarica	<i>Leptospira</i> in natural populations of small wild mammals
[138]	Widiyanti <i>et al.</i> (2019)	Scopus	Indonesia	Zoonoses and Public Health	Presence of bacteria in the environment, especially during floods
[76]	Houéménou <i>et al.</i> (2019)	Scopus	Benin	Urban Science	<i>Leptospira</i> in commensal small mammals
[166]	Sabri <i>et al.</i> (2019)	Scopus	Malaysia	Tropical Biomedicine	<i>Leptospira</i> sp. in cattle and goats after a massive flood
[55]	Rahmat <i>et al.</i> (2019)	Scopus	Malaysia	International Journal of	Prediction model for leptospirosis cases

				Integrated Engineering	
[156]	Hamond <i>et al.</i> (2019)	Scopus	Uruguay	Transboundary and Emerging Diseases	Report of ovine leptospirosis
[56]	Moreira <i>et al.</i> (2019)	Scopus	Brazil	Revista Brasileira de Geografia Física	Climatic factors, precipitation, and leptospirosis
[184]	Mohammadinia <i>et al.</i> (2019)	Scopus	Iran	BMC Infectious Diseases	Leptospirosis distribution and environmental modeling
[54]	Gutiérrez <i>et al.</i> (2019)	Scopus	Colombia	Cadernos de Saúde Pública	Environmental, socioeconomic variables and human leptospirosis
[107]	Ehelepola <i>et al.</i> (2019)	Scopus	Sri Lanka	Global Health Action	Human leptospirosis incidence and weather correlations
[110]	Duarte & Giatti (2019)	Scopus	Brazil	Epidemiologia e Serviços de Saúde	Environmental variables and leptospirosis incidence
[90]	Deshmukh <i>et al.</i> (2019)	Scopus	India	Clinical Epidemiology and Global Health	Epidemiology and climatic determinants of leptospirosis
[224]	Sasmal <i>et al.</i> (2019)	Scopus	USA	Journal of Wildlife Diseases	Leptospirosis in urban and suburban american black bears
[32]	López <i>et al.</i> (2019)	Scopus	Argentina	Science of the Total Environment	Hydro-climatic factors in disease occurrence in humans
[213]	Alhoot <i>et al.</i> (2019)	Scopus	Malaysia	International Journal of Medical Toxicology and Legal Medicine	Climate change and infectious diseases
[53]	Lara <i>et al.</i> (2019)	Scopus	Brazil	Revista Brasileira de Epidemiologia	Leptospirosis, climate, and sociodemographics
[140]	Sumalapao <i>et al.</i> (2019)	Scopus	Philippines	Asian Pacific Journal of Tropical Medicine	Relationship between typhoons and increased disease occurrence in humans
[115]	Péres <i>et al.</i> (2019)	Scopus	Brazil	Water	Influence of extreme hydrometeorological events and increased human hospitalization rates due to leptospirosis in Santa Catarina state

[28]	Sato <i>et al.</i> (2019)	Pubmed	Japan	Scientific Reports	Pathogenic <i>Leptospira</i> and associated organisms in leptospirosis-endemic areas
[130]	Goh <i>et al.</i> (2019)	Pubmed	Malaysia	International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health	Rat contact and shared areas as risk factors for shelter dogs and their handlers
[148]	Rahelinirina <i>et al.</i> (2019)	Pubmed	Madagascar	The American Journal of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene	Prevalence of <i>Leptospira</i> spp. in rodents
[139]	Ding <i>et al.</i> (2019)	Pubmed	China	Environmental Research	Influence of floods on human cases
[19]	Cucchi <i>et al.</i> (2019)	Pubmed	China	PLoS Neglected Tropical Diseases	Soil reservoir of pathogenic <i>Leptospira</i> spp.
[40]	Arias-Monsalve & Builes-Jaramillo (2019)	Pubmed	Colombia	Journal of Infection in Developing Countries	Leptospirosis during La Niña and El Niño episodes
[78]	Zhang <i>et al.</i> (2020)	Scopus	China	Transboundary and Emerging Diseases	Human leptospirosis
[201]	Thiruvengadam & Sultana (2020)	Scopus	India	Disaster Advances	Environmental contamination of spirochetes and accounts for leptospirosis
[114]	Baki <i>et al.</i> (2020)	Scopus	Malaysia	Malaysian Journal of Microbiology	Detection of pathogenicity genes in environmental samples
[101]	Rahmat <i>et al.</i> (2020)	Scopus	Malaysia	Frontiers in Earth Science	Leptospirosis occurrence and climate variables
[77]	Luenam & Puttanapong (2020)	Scopus	Thailand	Geospatial Health	Environmental factors to leptospirosis incidence and distribution
[167]	Tsai <i>et al.</i> (2020)	Scopus	Taiwan	Zoonoses and Public Health	Human leptospirosis and association with animals
[57]	Dhewantara <i>et al.</i> (2020)	Scopus	China	Science of Total Environment	Socioeconomic, environmental factors, leptospirosis distribution

[116]	Chery <i>et al.</i> (2020)	Scopus	Saint Lucia	Revista Panamericana de Salud Pública	Human epidemiology and correlation with precipitation and temperature
[171]	Koval <i>et al.</i> (2020)	Scopus	Argentina	Revista Argentina de Microbiologia	Case report of bovine leptospirosis
[203]	Zakharova <i>et al.</i> (2020)	Scopus	Russia	Pathogens	Leptospirosis exposure and environmental determinants
[204]	Silva <i>et al.</i> (2020)	Scopus	Brazil	Revista da Sociedade Brasileira de Medicina Tropical	Environmental, climatic, demographic factors, leptospirosis
[79]	Cerveira <i>et al.</i> (2020)	Scopus	Brazil	Revista Brasileira de Epidemiologia	Spatio-temporal analysis of leptospirosis
[112]	Hacker <i>et al.</i> (2020)	Pubmed	Brazil	Emerging Infectious Diseases	Leptospirosis incidence and rainfall
[208]	Rajapakse <i>et al.</i> (2020)	Pubmed	Sri Lanka	PLoS Neglected Tropical Diseases	Leptospirosis seroprevalence, geographic patterns, and risk factors
[33]	Silva <i>et al.</i> (2020)	Pubmed	Brazil	Geospatial Health	Identifying human disease clusters in municipalities after natural disasters
[179]	Moreira <i>et al.</i> (2020)	Pubmed	Portugal	BMJ Case Reports	Weil's disease in a young homeless man
[157]	Rahman <i>et al.</i> (2020)	Scopus	Malaysia	Journal of Veterinary Research	Disease prevalence in cattle, goats, and sheep after flooding
[14]	Taylor <i>et al.</i> (2021)	Scopus	Great Britain	Preventive Veterinary Medicine	Disease prevalence in dogs
[185]	Zakharova <i>et al.</i> (2021)	Scopus	Russia	Frontiers in Veterinary Science	Infection exposure and environmental determinants
[58]	Kira <i>et al.</i> (2021)	Scopus	Malaysia	Tropical Biomedicine	Environmental conditions and human leptospirosis
[104]	Pustahija <i>et al.</i> (2021)	Scopus	Serbia	Archives of Veterinary Medicine	Epidemiological characteristics of leptospirosis
[98]	Gutiérrez (2021)	Scopus	Colombia	International Journal of Biometeorology	Precipitation, temperature, and incidence
[117]	Gracie <i>et al.</i> (2021)	Scopus	Brazil	Cadernos de Saúde Pública	Higher risk of human leptospirosis in municipalities that declared floods

[169]	Brenea <i>et al.</i> (2021)	Scopus	Russia	Health Risk Analysis	Human leptospirosis after flood
[210]	Obaidat <i>et al.</i> (2021)	Scopus	Jordan	Transactions of the Royal Society of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene	Seroprevalence and risk factors of <i>Leptospira</i>
[91]	Maleki <i>et al.</i> (2021)	Scopus	Iran	Journal of Veterinary Research	Leptospirosis seroprevalence in livestock and environmental risk factors
[181]	Mgode <i>et al.</i> (2021)	Scopus	Tanzania	Pathogens	Disease prevalence in cattle, humans and wild animals
[59]	Warnasekara <i>et al.</i> (2021)	Scopus	Sri Lanka	PLoS ONE	Multivariate analysis of leptospirosis variables
[82]	Biscornet <i>et al.</i> (2021)	Scopus	Seychelles	Remote Sensing	Environmental factors influencing <i>Leptospira</i> infection in rodents
[209]	Houéménou <i>et al.</i> (2021)	Scopus	Benin	Science of the Total Environment	Presence of pathogenic <i>Leptospira</i> in urban waters
[80]	Jeske <i>et al.</i> (2021)	Scopus	Spain	Journal of Wildlife Diseases	Prevalence of <i>Leptospira</i> spp. in voles
[92]	Ehelepola <i>et al.</i> (2021)	Scopus	Sri Lanka	Tropical Medicine and Health	Correlation between three teleconnections and leptospirosis incidence
[158]	Keenum <i>et al.</i> (2021)	Scopus	Puerto Rico	Environmental Science and Technology	Presence of bacteria in water systems after flooding
[223]	Teixeira <i>et al.</i> (2021)	Scopus	Brazil	Acta Veterinaria Brasilica	Leptospirosis in cart horses and risk factors
[83]	Salcedo <i>et al.</i> (2021)	Scopus	Argentina	International Journal for Parasitology: Parasites and Wildlife	Role of <i>Mus musculus</i> in the transmission of several pathogens
[168]	Viroj <i>et al.</i> (2021)	Scopus	Thailand	Tropical Medicine and Infectious Disease	Agro-environmental determinants of leptospirosis
[34]	Syakbanah & Fuad (2021)	Scopus	Indonesia	Jurnal Kesehatan Lingkungan	Human disease cases after a cyclone and flooding
[81]	Convertino <i>et al.</i> (2021)	Scopus	USA	Science of the Total Environment	Pattern-based model to predict leptospirosis outbreaks
[194]	Miller <i>et al.</i> (2021)	Pubmed	Ecuador	BMC Microbiology	<i>Leptospira</i> in river and soil

[118]	Chadsuthi <i>et al.</i> (2021)	Scopus	Thailand	Scientific Reports	Mathematical model to evaluate cases in humans, animals, and the environment
[190]	Ma Yan <i>et al.</i> (2021)	Pubmed	Sweden	Scientific Reports	Climate-disease relationships in the Northern/Arctic Region
[84]	Cano-Pérez <i>et al.</i> (2021)	Pubmed	Colombia	The American Journal of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene	Climatic variability and human leptospirosis cases
[180]	Retnowati <i>et al.</i> (2022)	Scopus	Indonesia	Sains Malaysiana	<i>Leptospira</i> serovars and canine risks
[62]	Taunton <i>et al.</i> (2022)	Scopus	Australia	Communicable Diseases Intelligence	Occurrence of human leptospirosis after heavy rains and flooding
[170]	Becirovic <i>et al.</i> (2022)	Scopus	Bosnia and Herzegovina	Materia Socio-Medica	Floods associated with environmental factors and leptospirosis
[119]	Nelson <i>et al.</i> (2022)	Scopus	Fiji	Journal of Climate Change and Health	Seasonality and rainfall predict outbreaks of leptospirosis
[86]	Mai <i>et al.</i> (2022)	Scopus	Vietnam	International Journal of Infectious Diseases	Human leptospirosis in three different geographical and climatic zones
[93]	Brown <i>et al.</i> (2022)	Scopus	Australia	Communicable Diseases Intelligence	Leptospirosis outbreak linked to rainfall and cattle exposure
[42]	Silva <i>et al.</i> (2022)	Scopus	Brazil	Ciência e Saúde Coletiva	Climatic and environmental factors in human leptospirosis occurrence
[221]	Gabriel-Véjar <i>et al.</i> (2022)	Scopus	Mexico	Transboundary and Emerging Diseases	Spatial distribution models of seroreactive sheep to <i>Leptospira</i> spp.
[111]	Douchet <i>et al.</i> (2022)	Scopus	New Caledonia	Science of Total Environment	Seasonality, precipitation, temperature, leptospirosis
[61]	Warnasekara <i>et al.</i> (2022)	Scopus	Sri Lanka	PLoS ONE	Leptospirosis forecast using time series
[102]	Phosri (2022)	Scopus	Thailand	Stochastic Environmental Research and Risk Assessment	Rainfall and human leptospirosis association

[197]	Artus <i>et al.</i> (2022)	Scopus	USA	PLoS Neglected Tropical Diseases	Seroprevalence, distribution, and risk factors for human leptospirosis
[85]	Costa <i>et al.</i> (2022)	Scopus	Brazil	Transactions of the Royal Society of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene	Climate influence the human leptospirosis cases
[186]	Chadsuthi <i>et al.</i> (2022)	Scopus	Thailand	Scientific Reports	Spatial-temporal patterns and risk factors for human leptospirosis
[60]	Gómez <i>et al.</i> (2022)	Scopus	Argentina	Heliyon	Ecological model with hydroclimatic variables
[99]	Cunha <i>et al.</i> (2022)	Pubmed	Brazil	PLoS Neglected Tropical Disease	Leptospirosis incidence and weather anomalies
[131]	Yanagihara <i>et al.</i> (2022)	Pubmed	Japan	Microbiology Spectrum	Presence of <i>Leptospira</i> in the environment
[229]	Sluydts <i>et al.</i> (2022)	Pubmed	Sri Lanka	PLoS Neglected Tropical Diseases	Ecology and distribution of <i>Leptospira</i> spp., reservoir hosts and environmental interaction
[153]	Eyre <i>et al.</i> (2022)	Pubmed	Brazil	eLife	Rat abundance and environmental factors to human leptospirosis risk in urban communities
[141]	Marteli <i>et al.</i> (2022)	Pubmed	Brazil	Geospatial Health	Flood-prone areas and human leptospirosis cases
[191]	Kiuno <i>et al.</i> (2023)	Scopus	Japan	Animals	Epidemiological study of pathogenic <i>Leptospira</i> in raccoons.
[87]	Stark <i>et al.</i> (2023)	Scopus	Australia	Communicable Diseases Intelligence	Leptospirosis cases associated with crocodile workers
[63]	Jayaramu <i>et al.</i> (2023)	Scopus	Malaysia	International Journal of Biometeorology	Hydrometeorological risk factors and human leptospirosis
[172]	Rahman <i>et al.</i> (2023)	Scopus	Malaysia	Sains Malaysiana	Presence of <i>Leptospira</i> in cattle farm soils after flooding
[198]	Mugabe <i>et al.</i> (2023)	Scopus	Mozambique	Frontiers in Tropical Diseases	Cyclones Idai and Kenneth heightened the risk of leptospirosis

[132]	Udayar <i>et al.</i> (2023)	Scopus	India	Indian Journal of Community Medicine	Environmental risk factors associated with human leptospirosis
[210]	Shirzad <i>et al.</i> (2023)	Scopus	Iran	BMC Public Health	Spatio-temporal modeling of human leptospirosis
[175]	Sohn-Hausner <i>et al.</i> (2023)	Scopus	Brazil	Tropical Medicine and Infectious Disease	Leptospirosis seroprevalence in humans and dogs
[94]	Dreesman <i>et al.</i> (2023)	Scopus	Germany	Zoonoses and Public Health	Investigation and response to a large outbreak of leptospirosis in field workers
[65]	Mazzanti <i>et al.</i> (2023)	Scopus	Argentina	Frontiers in Veterinary Science	<i>Leptospira</i> antibodies in beef cattle
[193]	Lu <i>et al.</i> (2023)	Scopus	Australia	Veterinary Sciences	Landscape, socioeconomic, and meteorological risk factors for canine leptospirosis
[64]	Rees <i>et al.</i> (2023)	Scopus	Fiji	PLOS Global Public Health	Climate indicators and leptospirosis incidence
[133]	Sohn-Hausner <i>et al.</i> (2023)	Scopus	Brazil	Tropical Medicine and Infectious Disease	Risk factors such as flooding and serovars in dogs and their owners
[159]	Marić <i>et al.</i> (2023)	Scopus	Bosnia and Herzegovina	Acta Veterinaria	Seroprevalence of leptospirosis in dogs and foxes after flooding
[160]	Chiani <i>et al.</i> (2023)	Scopus	Argentina	Applied and Environmental Microbiology	<i>Leptospira</i> presence and environmental conditions
[123]	Edwards <i>et al.</i> (2023)	Scopus	Haiti	Air Medical Journal	A case review series during air medical transport
[95]	Kuloglu <i>et al.</i> (2023)	Scopus	Turkey	Revista do Instituto de Medicina Tropical de São Paulo	First report of human infection with <i>Leptospira interrogans</i> serovar Bratislava in the Eastern Black Sea region of Turkey
[227]	Garcia & Gopalakrishna (2023)	Pubmed	Puerto Rico	Cureus	A case of imported leptospirosis.
[220]	Motto <i>et al.</i> (2023)	Pubmed	Tanzania	PLoS Neglected Tropical Diseases	Seroepidemiology of <i>Leptospira</i> serovar Hardjo and associated risk factors in

					smallholder dairy cattle
[205]	Lotto Batista <i>et al.</i> (2023)	Scopus	Argentina	Journal of the Royal Society Interface	Hydrometeorological indicators and outbreak prediction
[124]	Yamamoto <i>et al.</i> (2023)	Pubmed	Japan	The American Journal of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene	Leptospirosis after a typhoon disaster outside the endemic region.
[43]	Hagiya <i>et al.</i> (2023)	Pubmed	Japan	The American Journal of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene	Epidemiological characteristics of leptospirosis
[88]	Antima & Banerjee (2023)	Pubmed	India	Scientific Reports	Dynamics of leptospirosis through a mathematical model
[212]	Jones <i>et al.</i> (2024)	Scopus	Puerto Rico	Morbidity and Mortality Weekly Report	Leptospirosis cases and hurricane
[108]	Sutiningsih <i>et al.</i> (2024)	Scopus	Indonesia	Tropical Medicine and Infectious Disease	Geospatial analysis of abiotic and biotic conditions associated with leptospirosis
[22]	Thibeaux <i>et al.</i> (2024)	Scopus	New Caledonia	Science of the Total Environment	Presence of <i>Leptospira</i> in soil samples after floods
[188]	Montenegro-Idrogo <i>et al.</i> (2024)	Scopus	Colombia	Transactions of the Royal Society of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene	Spatiotemporal analysis, hydroclimatic factors and human leptospirosis
[143]	Poulakida <i>et al.</i> (2024)	Scopus	Greece	Infectious Disease Reports	Flooding impact on leptospirosis incidence
[176]	Ifejube <i>et al.</i> (2024)	Scopus	India	International Journal of Health Geographics	Positive relationship between flooding and human cases
[215]	Petakh <i>et al.</i> (2024)	Scopus	Ukraine	One Health	Geographical factors and air raid alarms influence leptospirosis epidemiology
[142]	Rodríguez-Rodríguez <i>et al.</i> (2024)	Scopus	Colombia	Zoonoses and Public Health	Risk factors for leptospirosis occurrence in humans
[89]	Manjunathachar <i>et al.</i> (2024)	Scopus	India	Indian Journal of Medical Microbiology	Human leptospirosis
[41]	Sato <i>et al.</i> (2024)	Scopus	Palau	One Health	Environmental risk for leptospirosis
[44]	Bridgemohan <i>et al.</i> (2024)	Scopus	USA	Journal of Water and Health	Susceptibility of coastal ecosystems to zoonotic pathogens

[206]	Akbar <i>et al.</i> (2024)	Scopus	Indonesia	Jurnal Kesehatan Lingkungan	Density of <i>Rattus norvegicus</i> and the associated with flooding, poor drainage, and waste accumulation
[149]	Katsafourou <i>et al.</i> (2024)	Scopus	Greece	Hippokratia	Leptospirosis outbreak linked to catastrophic floods
[150]	Soni <i>et al.</i> (2024)	Scopus	Brazil	Frontiers in Public Health	Leptospirosis spillover linked to flooding and environmental factors
[35]	Douchet <i>et al.</i> (2024)	Pubmed	New Caledonia	PLoS Neglected Tropical Diseases	Seasonality, precipitation, temperature, leptospirosis
[200]	Han <i>et al.</i> (2024)	Pubmed	China	Clinical Case Reports	A case report of human leptospirosis after typhoon events